

Study Protocol: Financial incentives to increase willingness to work during pandemics:

A rapid realist review

1. Introduction

The structure of this protocol follows published realist review protocols (1, 2).

1.1. Background

There has been a renewed policy interest in preparing and strengthening healthcare systems for periods of crisis in light of the Covid-19 pandemic and recent geopolitical tensions (3-5). A crucial aspect of preparing healthcare systems for crises is ensuring adequate staffing, especially among healthcare workers caring for patients; to borrow a WHO title: ‘A universal truth: no health without a workforce’ (6). Research has revealed that health care workers caring for patients face additional challenges during health care emergencies, including higher workloads, higher levels of fear, stress, and burnout, and even moral challenges, causing moral distress, which increases the risk of absenteeism and job turnover (7, 8).

One concept that has received substantial attention in relation to public health emergencies and staffing is the concept of willingness to work. A simple definition is that willingness to work is the intention or wanting to provide care, not the preparedness level or ability, and is related to motivation to work (9, 10). Willingness to work is said to predict whether or not someone will work in a public health crisis (10). Retaining high levels of willingness can therefore mitigate outcomes like absenteeism (11). Previous research has shown that willingness to work during crises varies substantially. A systematic review found that willingness to work during public health emergencies varied between 23% to 96% (12). Review studies have identified factors associated with willingness to work during public health emergencies (13-17) and for more specific crises, like respiratory disease outbreaks (10) and influenza pandemics (12). Lee et al. (10) classified the barriers and facilitators into seven categories: demographics, attitude, perceived norm, personal agency, knowledge and skills to perform the behaviour, environmental constraints, and habits.

One of the most popular measures during the Covid-19 pandemic was providing direct financial support, like bonuses, a higher monthly salary, a lump sum, tax exemptions or the like (18, 19). Despite its popularity at the policy level, direct financial support has received sparse attention in the research literature (10), and primary studies have reached conflicting results on whether it can increase willingness to work during pandemics. Some have concluded that financial

support, in the case of double pay, is a negative predictor of willingness (20) and when financial support is perceived as unfair, it can disincentivise work (21). Komasa et al. found that, after adjusting for confounders, direct financial support does not correlate with motivation to work (22). Moreover, it has been suggested that external incentives have little impact on nurses' willingness in crises if they are invested in their role (23). On the contrary, several studies have found that direct financial support is correlated with higher levels of willingness (19, 24-27) and that the absence of appropriate financial support can decrease willingness (28). This is supported by qualitative studies that found that for some people, financial incentives can be an important motivator in crises (29-31).

1.2. Added value of a realist review

As noted above, several reviews have explored willingness to work during pandemics. What can this review add?

This is the first review study focusing specifically on financial incentives. A realist review addresses questions like why, when, for whom, and under what circumstances an intervention works. Answering these questions in relation to direct financial support is important for researchers and policymakers to prepare for future pandemics.

Previous review studies have mapped factors associated with willingness to work. This has provided important insight into facilitators and barriers to willingness to work. But there are inherent explanatory limits to this methodology, where the aim is to combine data to measure effectiveness; a realist review aims to identify the underlying causal processes (32). Previous studies have shown that financial incentives sometimes work and sometimes don't work. We still don't know *why* financial interventions affect willingness to work and produce these – prima facie – conflicting outcomes. This question can be addressed with a realist approach, and this knowledge is necessary for tailoring interventions. On a realist view, interventions don't cause outcomes to occur, but alter the context in which agents operate: “when an intervention is introduced, it changes the context (by providing further reasoning, opportunities, permissions, legitimations, authorizations, and limitations), so presenting people with a different set of circumstances in which to exercise agency, leading to different outcomes” (33).

A previous realist review on interventions to tackle doctors' mental ill-health noted that most interventions focus on the individual traits of the doctors, which “neglects the organisational and structural contexts that may have a detrimental effect on doctors' well-being” (34). A similar methodological individualism is present in the literature on willingness to work, where different

factors are construed as conditioned by individual-level circumstances. No review has synthesised how broader systematic factors interact with personal-level factors to produce differences in willingness to work. This is especially relevant for the literature on financial incentives, where studies have concluded that financial incentives are only effective if other organisational support measures are in place. For example, several studies have shown that for many healthcare workers, financial incentives have no effect if adequate protective measures for self and family are absent (20). Realists hold that outcomes are dependent on context, and their idea of generative causation is expressed by the Context+Mechanism→Outcome (CMO) configuration. An important part of a realist synthesis is explaining how the context triggers the mechanism to produce the outcome (35). A realist approach, where context is multi-layered (individuals, interpersonal relations, institution and infrastructure), is perfectly suited for studying these dynamic interactions (36).

2. Conducting a realist review

The reporting and quality standards for Realist and Meta-narrative Evidence Syntheses: Evolving Standards (RAMESES) (37, 38) will guide all stages of the work, and the review will take its starting point in the five steps for realist reviews proposed by Pawson et al (39):

Step 1. Clarify the review scope

Step 2: Develop an initial programme theory

Step 3: Searching for evidence

Step 4: Selection and appraisal

Step 5. Extract and synthesise data

A realist review, however, is not a linear process, but flexible and iterative. This means that, especially from Step 3 onwards, the process often becomes circular, leading up to the final programme theory.

I have chosen to call this a rapid realist review. The reason for this is that a typical realist review is conducted within a multidisciplinary team and takes around 12-18 months (35). Since this review will be conducted by a single person, some steps will be shortened. Realist methodologists have argued that any stage of a realist review can be shortened if the authors are explicit about the shortcuts and discuss how cutting corners will impact the findings (ibid).

The stakeholder group will assist in shortening the review process. We will lean on their knowledge when deciding what to focus on. These discussions and the decisions will be reported in the final paper (39).

2.1 Clarify the review scope

The first step in a realist review is to decide the scope by defining review objectives and questions. To do this, a brief, informal search was conducted. Booth et al. describe how different search strategies are used at different stages of realist reviews (40). An informal background search is often used early in the review. This search aims to identify relevant literature and cast a wide net over the literature to find relevant articles and understand the terrain. Common strategies include looking for highly cited articles, forward citation tracking, backward citation tracking, and searching for review articles (41).

The background search focused on factors associated with willingness and papers on direct financial support (see appendix 1 for search terms).

Objectives

1. Develop a programme theory explaining why, for whom, and in what circumstances, direct financial support impacts willingness to work during pandemics
2. Make policy recommendations about direct financial support as an intervention strategy to increase the willingness to work during pandemics

Questions

1. Why does direct financial support influence healthcare workers' willingness to work during pandemics? What are the mechanisms at work?
2. In what contexts, and for whom, can direct financial support influence healthcare workers' willingness to work during pandemics?

The review's scope will be decided upon by the stakeholders in a meeting scheduled for March 2026.

2.2. Develop an initial programme theory

Realist reviews are theory-driven reviews. The aim of a realist review in the Pawson-Tilly tradition is to provide a *programme theory*. A programme theory explains why, when, and for whom an intervention works. As seen previously, realists believe in a particular view of

generative causation: context + mechanism → outcome. CMO configurations are the constituent parts of a programme theory.

CMO configurations, and hence program theories, can be formulated at different levels of abstraction. A realist programme theory should be formulated at a level called “middle-range” (42). A middle-range theory has primarily two features: It’s concrete enough to admit to empirical testing, but general enough to be transferable to analogous situations (ibid).

The first step in developing this theory is to develop an initial programme theory. This initial theory structures the review and governs the upcoming steps. This theory doesn’t necessarily need to be formulated in realist language, but the final version must be realist (37).

The programme theory is currently being developed (see page 6) and will be finalised in a stakeholder meeting in March 2026. Some formal theories were identified in the background search. Formal theories can play an important role in, for example, identifying contexts and mechanisms and explaining how the different CMO configurations hang together (43).

2.3: Searching for evidence

The search stage aims to collect data to test and develop the theory. Although a comprehensive search is important, the aim is not necessarily to exhaust the literature. Realist reviews are a form of configurational synthesis, not an aggregative one, and more data does not enhance explanatory power or the trustworthiness of the theory (44).

The search will be developed with a librarian. Developing the search with a librarian is something that has been highlighted as important for realist reviews (45), and this is especially important for our review. There is no agreed-upon definition of the concept of willingness to work, which means that relevant papers span across several domains and concepts. We will attempt to sample from different types of databases, not only health databases, and databases will include Google Scholar, PubMed, Embase, Cochrane, Scopus, Medline and PsycINFO. We will also hold stakeholder consultations, conduct citation searching (forward and backwards), and ask topic experts to find relevant literature (41).

As the programme theory develops, further searches may become necessary.

Inclusion criteria:

Population: Healthcare workers in direct contact with patients

Intervention: Any intervention offering direct financial support to healthcare workers, including but not limited to, hazard pay, a bonus, a higher salary, a lump sum, tax exemption, an insurance package, direct payments

Setting: Pandemics and epidemics that result in public health emergencies, where public health emergencies are defined as “a period of heightened difficulty, danger, or uncertainty, often precipitated by unforeseen events that disrupt the standard operational frameworks within healthcare settings” (46). Studies focusing on crises simpliciter will be included if the data on pandemics/epidemics can be disaggregated.

Outcome: Willingness and motivation to work

Study design: All study designs will be included

Study type: All document types will be included, including grey literature and non-empirical literature. No type of evidence is excluded a priori in realist reviews.

Exclusion criteria:

- *Adjacent concepts:* Studies focusing on adjacent concepts, like cognitive preparedness will not be included in this study

- *Other crises*: Studies focusing on other public health emergencies, like wars and natural disasters, will not be included.

The background search revealed that the literature is sparse. Limiting the review to high-income countries wouldn't be feasible (see limitations below for a discussion on this).

2.4: Selection and Appraisal

The appraisal stage has been criticised in realist reviews. Many researchers don't define the criteria and/or make the process opaque (47). Theory building, and by extension selection of evidence, must be a transparent process; otherwise, it becomes like "magicking out of a hat" (48). To make the process as transparent as possible, the selection and appraisal process will be documented carefully.

Realist reviews follow the same screening process as traditional systematic reviews: first, titles/abstracts are screened. The documents that pass through title/abstract screening will be read in full, appraised for *relevance*, *richness*, and *rigour*. At both stages, 10% will be screened by an additional person (a colleague). Disagreements will be resolved via discussion. Any additional search(es) will follow the same screening process. The 10% double screening follows previous realist reviews (1).

The first criterion is relevance, i.e. whether the material can help build - does it help explain mechanisms or context? - or test the theory (38). It's important to have a dynamic conception of relevance; irrelevant documents can become important as the theory changes. The second criterion is rigour. Rigour, at the level of data, is defined by the RAMESES quality standards as: "whether the method used to generate that piece of data is credible and 'trustworthy'" (38). Rigour isn't solely an inherent feature of the quality of the included documents but also relates to the programme theory under development and to the other evidence. Even studies with a potentially high risk of bias can have sections that are considered sufficiently rigorous to be included in the study (47). The last criteria are *richness*. Richness is the inherent explanatory power of the data for the theory (47). Both conceptual richness (*how* it works) and contextual thickness (where and when it works) should be used to assess richness. To make this assessment criterion more transparent, we will use (and report) a scoring system where the papers will be judged on a scale from 1 to 5. Papers with low richness will not be prioritised (at this stage, given the programme theory). These criteria will be defined and reported once the initial programme theory is finalised.

Since we are doing a rapid realist review, if needed, relevance, rigour and richness can be defined narrowly to ensure that we end up with a manageable number of documents to synthesise. Moreover, we can also focus on rich documents, since they are most useful for theory building. The choices will be reported, and the impacts on the findings will be discussed.

2.5. Data extraction and synthesis

The following information will be extracted from the included documents: Authors, Title, Year, Study methods, Population (and n=), Setting, Country, Intervention(s), Aim(s), Key findings.

The extraction and the analysis/synthesis processes are interlinked; coding the data into nodes and working with these nodes is a form of analysis. Here, the two stages have been separated for clarity.

Data extraction in realist reviews is always done in relation to a theory; the aim is not to ‘carve nature [or the data] at its joints’ but to explain why an intervention works, for whom, and in what circumstances. Any information explaining these aspects is relevant to extract.

We will follow the data extraction and initial coding steps outlined by Gilmore et al. (49), keeping in mind that realist reviews are flexible and iterative. The data extraction process often starts already when studies are appraised for relevance, richness and rigour (1). At this stage, using Nvivo, nodes with accompanying memos (relevant contextual information about the node) will be created for the different parts of the initial programme theory. CMO configurations will be identified and coded to different nodes and sub-nodes. These will, at first, be of a low level of abstractions and ‘close to the data’. These nodes will be generated using deductive reasoning (deducing from the initial programme theory), inductive reasoning (finding patterns and generalising from the data), and retroductive reasoning. In retroductive reasoning, one starts with the outcome and infers what the world must be like for that outcome to obtain; the underlying causal mechanisms and the contexts are inferred from the programme's effect (50).

After the documents have been coded, there will likely be a plethora of different CMO configurations. Similar CMO configurations will be merged (50). The configurations will be given a conceptual label to identify demi-regularities. The different parts of the theory will be combined and synthesised into a programme theory. This process will require different methods of analysis: Juxtaposition, reconciliation, and consolidation (51). Through this process, the

CMO configurations will be formulated at a higher level of abstraction that allows for empirical testing and transferability; the theory will become middle-range.

Importantly, the quality of a theory isn't just a feature of its trustworthiness:

“(..) to (for example) develop a theory, data need to be identified as being relevant, analysed, inferences made and arguments and theory constructed. Hence, judgements about ‘quality’ need to be made, for all of these processes and at the very least at the levels of data, argument and theory” (51).

Put differently, the inferences and arguments from data to theory are as important as the features of the theory, like explanatory power.

Further searches will likely become necessary. All changes from the initial programme theory to the final theory will be reported, using the methods described by Gilmore et al. (49), so that readers can tell how and why the theory was refined.

The stakeholder group will be involved in the extraction and synthesis process. There will be two separate meetings during this stage. First, a meeting after all the studies have been extracted and coded. The stakeholders will input on the coding and whether the tentative theory is trustworthy and plausible. Second, there will be a meeting to agree on the final version of the programme theory.

3. Limitations and stakeholder involvement

3.1. Limitations

A potential limitation with this review is that the studies are conducted in settings that are too different to form a unified programme theory. For a realist, context has two meanings: “(a) the literal backdrop within which events take place, such as policy and social factors, and (b) the relational, emergent, and dynamic forces that interact with mechanism, including cultural norms and relationships “ (52). Both these conditions will be carefully considered. However, if the (a) view of context is incompatible across the studies, more weight can be given to construing context as the relational and dynamic forces, where it will likely be easier to find similarities across studies. This will, of course, be highlighted and reported transparently. Future studies can then investigate how the literal backdrop interacts with relational and dynamic forces to serve as context.

Another potential limitation is that the evidence is not *rich* enough to build a programme theory. Much of the literature is quantitative; the preliminary search identified few rich sources. If the literature is too limited, even after searching with a librarian, to build a programme theory, we

will find ways to deal with this problem. This can be done, for example, by limiting the explanatory scope. Instead of attempting to formulate a transferable middle-range programme theory, we can attempt to formulate tentative CMO configurations or if-then statements for specific contexts jointly with the stakeholder group. This has been done previously when the data didn't allow for creating a theory, and ensures that the output is still of value to the stakeholder group (53).

Lastly, realist reviews are often done in multi-disciplinary teams. A solo realist review is inherently limited, practically in terms of what you can achieve alone, but also epistemologically. Realist epistemology opposes the myth of the given, that we stand in direct relation to raw sense data, and instead holds that knowledge is a theory-driven relation between the world and the knower (54). Knowledge always reflects both the world and the knowers' epistemic position. In virtue of having different epistemic positions, e.g. beliefs, perceptions, values, and social positions, a multi-disciplinary group has access to different (and more) empirical realities, compared to a solo reviewer. To minimise this inherent epistemological gap of conducting a solo review, we have gathered a diverse stakeholder group that will be involved throughout the review.

We will also include a section on reflexivity. This section will highlight how the researcher's epistemic position has impacted the results (54).

3.2. Stakeholder involvement

A stakeholder group will be set up and consulted with at different stages in the review, as reported above. Five individuals are part of the stakeholder group: a policymaker, a nurse working in an emergency department, a midwife, a medical student, and a member of the public.

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Appendix 1: Search strategy (protocol)

Database: Google Scholar Date: 20/10/2025

Search	Search terms	Results	Filter
1	(Nurse OR doctor OR physician* OR healthcare worker OR frontline worker OR hospital staff) AND (emergency OR disaster OR crises or crisis OR pandemic OR COVID OR epidemic) AND (willingness OR resilience OR turnover)	441,000	Page 1-20 screened
2	(realist synthesis OR realist review OR program theory OR programme theory) AND (willingness OR resilience OR turnover OR absenteeism) AND (emergency OR disaster OR crises OR pandemic OR COVID OR epidemic)	186,000	Page 1-10 screened

Database: PubMed Date: 21/10/2025 (updated search, 18/01/2026)

Search	Search terms	Results	Filter
<i>Block 1</i>			
1	health personnel [MeSH terms]	667,466	
2	"nurse*" [Title/Abstract] OR "doctor*" [Title/Abstract] OR "physician*" [Title/Abstract] OR "healthcare worker*" [Title/Abstract] OR "frontline worker*" [Title/Abstract] OR "hospital staff*" [Title/Abstract]	988,531	
3	#1 OR #2	1,406,997	
<i>Block 2</i>			
4	"emergenc*" [Title/Abstract] OR "disaster*" [Title/Abstract] OR "crisis" [Title/Abstract] OR "crises" [Title/Abstract] OR "disaster*" [Title/Abstract] OR "pandemic*" [Title/Abstract] OR "covid*" [Title/Abstract] OR "epidemic*" [Title/Abstract]	1,257,531	
Block 3			
5	"willingness to work" [Title/Abstract] OR "report to work" [Title/Abstract] OR "motivation to	2873	

Search	Search terms	Results	Filter
	work"[Title/Abstract] OR "turnover intention*"[Title/Abstract]		
Block 4			
6	"reimbursement, incentive"[MeSH Terms] OR "financial incentive*"[Title/Abstract] OR "hazard pay"[Title/Abstract] OR "bonus pay"[Title/Abstract] OR "bonus*"[Title/Abstract] OR "additional pay"[Title/Abstract] OR "remuneration"[Title/Abstract] OR "financial support"[Title/Abstract]		24,301
9	#3 AND #4 AND #5	368	
10	#3 AND #4 AND #5	27	Review, Systematic Reviews
11	#3 AND #4 AND #5 AND #6	9	